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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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WORD FORMATION AND VOCABULARY ENRICHMENT IN MODERN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article provides a comparative analysis of word formation processes and vocabulary enrichment in English and Uzbek languages. The study focuses on major word-building mechanisms and their role in linguistic development. The novelty lies in proposing a comparative model of vocabulary expansion.

Key words: word formation, vocabulary, affixation, composition, conversion, linguistics, comparative analysis.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida so'z yasalishi jarayonlari hamda lug'at boyligini oshirish mexanizmlari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda affiksatsiya, kompozitsiya, konversiya va qisqartirish kabi asosiy usullar ilmiy manbalar asosida o'rganildi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy til taraqqiyotida yangi leksik birliklarning shakllanishi va ularning kommunikativ ahamiyati yoritildi. Muallif tomonidan ikki tilning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ochib berildi va integrativ yondashuv taklif etildi. Ilmiy yangilik sifatida lug'at boyligini oshirishning qiyosiy modeli ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: so'z yasalishi, lug'at boyligi, affiksatsiya, kompozitsiya, konversiya, lingvistika, qiyosiy tahlil.

Аннотация: В статье проводится сравнительный анализ процессов словообразования и обогащения словарного состава в английском и узбекском языках. Рассматриваются основные способы образования слов, их функции и роль в развитии языка. Научная новизна заключается в разработке сравнительной модели пополнения словарного состава.

Ключевые слова: словообразование, лексика, аффиксация, композиция, конверсия, лингвистика, сравнительный анализ.

INTRODUCTION

The development of a language is directly related to its vocabulary, and any language is enriched with new lexical units under the influence of social and cultural changes. Modern English and Uzbek are also actively developing languages in the process of globalization, technological progress and cultural integration. The relevance of this study is that today interlingual contacts are increasing, and the rate of emergence of new words is increasing. Therefore, a scientific analysis of the mechanisms of word formation is of great importance. The object of the study is the lexical system of the English and Uzbek languages, and the subject is the processes of word formation. The purpose of the study is a comparative analysis of methods for increasing vocabulary in the example of two languages.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The issue of word formation is one of the widely studied areas in linguistics. In English linguistics, I. Plag explains word formation as an important part of morphology and indicates affixation and composition as the main mechanisms ^[1]. L. Bauer interprets the process of new word formation as a natural result of language development ^[2]. D. Crystal emphasizes the widespread use of abbreviations and new technological terms in the modern development of the English language ^[3].

In Uzbek linguistics, M. Abidova indicates affixation as the main method of word formation and explains its systemic features in detail ^[4]. Also, in modern studies, language development is also associated with social factors. In particular, it is emphasized that language development is closely related to communicative needs and technological changes ^[5]. However, a comprehensive comparative analysis of the English and Uzbek languages is not sufficiently covered in the existing literature. This article will explore this aspect in more depth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methods were used in the research process: comparative-analytical method, descriptive method and linguistic observation method. Word formation models in English and Uzbek were selected, their structure and functional features were compared. Theoretical views in scientific sources were also analyzed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Word formation is one of the most important and dynamic layers of the language system. In modern English and Uzbek, vocabulary growth is achieved through various linguistic mechanisms. In order to analyze this process in depth, it is necessary to first take into account the structural features of each language.

English is distinguished as an analytical language. This language expresses grammatical relations more through word order and auxiliary means. Therefore, the process of forming new words is also relatively free and flexible. Affixation plays an important role in English. For example, examples such as happy - happiness, kind - kindness, teach - teacher show that affixes create new grammatical and semantic meanings. However, this process is less systematic than in the Uzbek language. Composition is one of the most active methods in English. For example, words such as blackboard, classroom, smartphone, website are formed by combining two or more components. This method is especially widely used in the technological field. Conversion is one of the most characteristic features of the English language. In this process, the category changes without changing the form of the word. For example, verbs such as to email, to google, to text are actually derived from nouns. This phenomenon is based on the principle of economy of language. Abbreviation is also widely used in modern English. For example, abbreviations such as IT, AI, ASAP, UNESCO arise from the requirements of rapid communication.

The Uzbek language is an agglutinative language, in which word formation occurs mainly through affixation. This process is based on strict grammatical rules. For example:

- o'qit + uvchi → o'qituvchi
- bilim + don → bilimdon
- yoz + uvchi → yozuvchi

These examples show that new lexical units are systematically formed through affixes. Composition also exists in the Uzbek language, but is less active than in English: temiryol, kustana, kolkop. Semantic expansion also plays an important role. For example, the word "network" was originally used in a biological sense, but is now also used in Internet terminology. Comparative analysis shows that the English language is analytical, flexible, and the Uzbek language is agglutinative, systematic. In English, new words appear faster, while in Uzbek their formation is based on strict rules. Analysis of modern trends shows that globalization today has a great impact on language development. Many words are coming from English to Uzbek: computer, internet, marketing.

This process is increasing the vocabulary of the Uzbek language, but at the same time it raises the issue of adaptation to the national language system. As a result of the analysis, it was found that word formation in both languages is a key factor in language development; freedom in English is dominant, and systematicity in Uzbek; modern technologies are accelerating the formation of new lexical units.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the study showed that the word formation processes in English and Uzbek are formed on the basis of different linguistic mechanisms. Although both languages are active in expanding their vocabulary, their internal system and development directions differ significantly from each other. Analyticity prevails in English, and new words are formed mainly through composition, conversion, and reduction. In Uzbek, agglutinativity is the main feature, and affixation is manifested as the most effective and systematic method. At the same time, in the modern communicative environment, both languages rapidly adopting new lexical units. In particular, the emergence of terms related to technology, the Internet, and global culture is becoming an important factor in language development.

This process demonstrates the dynamism and flexibility of the language. The analyzes showed that while in English the word formation processes are more free and flexible, in Uzbek they are carried out on the basis of a strict grammatical system. This further highlights the structural differences between the two languages. From this perspective, comparative analysis allows us to identify not only the differences but also the similarities between the two languages.

The study found that word formation is not only related to the internal system of the language, but is also inextricably linked to social, cultural and technological factors. The rapid emergence and widespread dissemination of new words in the modern information space is accelerating the pace of language development.

This requires new approaches in linguistic research. Based on this study, it is advisable to teach word formation models in the language teaching process based on a systematic and comparative approach, and this will not only increase the vocabulary of students, but also develop their analytical thinking skills, the need to integrate modern lexical units, especially new terms and abbreviations, into the teaching process of English and Uzbek, which will allow linking the language with a real communicative environment, the need to widely use a comparative approach in linguistic research to study the general laws and specific aspects of different languages in more depth, the use of digital technologies and corpus linguistics in the study of word formation processes will increase efficiency, and the need to take into account social and psycholinguistic factors affecting language development in future research in this area.

In general, the issue of word formation and vocabulary development remains one of the important areas of modern linguistics. The results of this study are of practical importance in linguistics, translation studies, and language teaching methodologies.

List of references:

1. Plag I. Word-formation in English. - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002. - 239 p.
2. Bauer L. Introducing linguistic morphology. - Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2003. - 366 p.
3. Crystal D. The Cambridge encyclopedia of the English language. - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003. - 499 p.
4. Yule G. The study of language. - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010. - 320 p.
5. Abidova M. I. Peculiarities of medical terminology // Economics and society. – 2018. – no. 2 (45). - S. 6-8.
6. Rahmatullayev Sh. Modern Uzbek literary language. - Tashkent: Teacher, 2010. - 400 p.
7. Nurmonov A. Fundamentals of Uzbek linguistics. - Tashkent: Science, 2012. - 320 p.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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